

Educational Planning and Accessibility to Early Childhood Education in Rwanda

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Abstract: Around the world, several initiatives have been explored to improve access to education of young children. The researcher assessed the objectives which are to examine the elements of early childhood education planning; and establish a link between education planning and accessibility to early childhood education. There were 1,106 persons in the intended audience. Stratified, purposeful and fundamental randomness sample approaches were used for sampling. The sample size was 15 principals, two sector education officers, 47 teachers, and 46 parents (for a total of 110 respondents). As data gathering techniques, formal and semi-structured questionnaires were employed, as well as interviews and focus group discussions. The information gathered was examined both subjectively and quantitatively. The information was analyzed in accordance with the study's purpose, and the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) software, 16.0 version, was utilized to create the frequencies, means, and percentages that were used to describe the study's conclusions. The study's findings found that components of education planning in Gasabo District such as training of personnel, curriculum development and buildings, equipment and facilities were insufficient as confirmed by the majority of respondents. The studies also found that access to early childhood education was limited due to a lack of classrooms, a high pupil-to-teacher ratio, and the high cost of accessible nursery schools. The data also revealed a beneficial association between education planning and early childhood education accessibility. Based on the data, the researcher concluded that early childhood education availability in Gasabo District is limited due to poor education planning. According to the results and conclusions, the study suggests that education planners and policymakers invest adequate funding in the education sector to encourage early childhood education. This would aid in the training of trained early childhood educators, the supply of teaching and learning tools, and the building of new classrooms, particularly in remote regions.

Keywords: Accessibility to Early Childhood Education, Educational Planning.

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

The same Policy underlined the role of MINEDUC as being policy-maker and supervisor. It showed also that the government didn't, at the time, finance pre-school education, rather it offered technical assistance and planned to encourage the private sector to supply such services. The Government forecasted also to finance this sub-sector and to examine the viability of providing such services utilizing current Primary and other organizations.

In its first Early Child Development Policy in 2011, Rwanda Government planned to create at least one multi-service ECD Centre in every administrative sector by 2014/2015, in Rwanda. According to the publication, "pilot Community-based Integrated ECD Centers will be designed during 2011/2012, and implemented and evaluated in each District and Sector throughout the Strategic Plan's lifetime" (MINEDUC, 2011). In response to the issues raised by the EFA Action Plan, the Education Sector Policy made it a priority to ensure that education is available to all Rwandans, including pre-primary school-aged children (MINEDUC, 2003). Furthermore, the Ministry of Education defined 9 objectives for the

implementation of the 9YBE Program through the ESSP 2005-2010 in line with the EFA framework. The initial goal was to increase the availability of early childhood care and development.

The situation did not improve significantly according to MINEDUC, (as cited in Paxton, 2012); prior to the publication of the Child Development and Strategic Plan, little policy attention was paid to pre-primary education. Take-up remained quite low, however there was an uptick from 6.1% to little over 10% between 2010 and 2011. According to the same source, MINEDUC, the great bulk of this take-up should be in the private sector, given there were only two state nursery schools in Rwanda in 2010. Based on 2012 Rwanda Population and Housing Census, over 29% of the 1.28 million kids aged three to six years were enrolled in a pre-primary program. (MINECOFIN, 2014).

1.1 Problem statement

For many years, Early childhood education has been left behind around the World. EFA Global Monitoring Report (2008) states: “ECE programs generally do not reach the poorest and most disadvantaged children”, there are also differences in school involvement between areas or states, as well as between urban and rural regions. According to data collected from 17 nations, Education International (June 2010), some countries have made ECE an intrinsic component of the public education system, while others are working to raise the certification of ECE personnel and encourage males to choose ECE as a career. However, the ECE industry remains primarily private, and access to ECE remains limited, particularly for poor and rural children, as well as children with special needs, particularly in developing nations.

Even our country Rwanda didn't survive. The Ministry of Education (2011), through its Education Management Information System (2010), published that only 6.1% of kids of preschool age were registered in nursery schools. In choosing Gasabo District, the researcher has been motivated by the fact that the district has a big number of nursery schools. Many of them are private and others were currently attached to primary schools. However, a number of children enter in public primary education without having background in ECE. In addition, Gasabo District deals with two realities, which are reality of rural and reality of urban areas. And it is interesting to examine if there is difference in accessibility to ECE between them.

Several initiatives have been done. The policy was established through the ESSP 2005-2010. But the important initiative is an exponential increase of private pre-schools. But, the only way to escarp still to having a strong education planning. Within this context, this research aims to evaluate the link between Education Planning and Access to Early Childhood Education.

1.2 Specific Objectives

- (i) To investigate the availability of resources for early childhood education planning in Gasabo district.
- (ii) To develop a link between educational planning and access to education of young children in Gasabo district.

1.3 The Importance of the Research

This research would be relevant to a large number of individuals such as the Ministry of Education, stakeholders, and other investigators who might be interested in it. The researcher has extensive understanding of early childhood education, particularly in Gasabo District, before completing this investigation. For Education Ministry and other stakeholders, the present study would help to enhance the future policies in the domain of Education for Young Children, by developing standardized curriculum, by planning for infrastructures and facilities and by training teachers to permit to all children aged between 3 and 6 years to access pre-primary schools effectively. It would also motivate other researchers to continue to investigate in the field, using our findings as inspiration. The study would also serve as source of knowledge for other stakeholders about the challenges of the accessibility to early childhood education.

1.4 Study Limitation

The clear limitation of this research had relationship with studies conducted before. Early childhood is a concept known, but the formal education at this stage is not yet developed in Rwanda, regarding Education Sector Policy. Thus, the study did not get enough copies of documents about it. Electronic documents were used to overcome the challenge.

Another issue is the fact that we could not generalize the findings in this study to other regions because they were not subjected to the same socio-economic or geographic conditions.

1.5 Geographical Scope

Our study covered Gasabo District, located in Kigali City, administrative capital of Rwanda. The motivation for choice was socio-demographic and political situation of the region. The District of Gasabo is one of three districts which make up Kigali City.

It is situated in north part of Rwanda Capital. The big part of it is rural and the remaining one is urban. So, a variety of data for our study could be collected and generalized both for rural region and urban one.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical literature, empirical literature, critical evaluation and study gaps, theoretical framework, conceptual framework, and summary are all covered in this chapter.

2.1 Theoretical Literature

This point is concerned with Education planning for education of young children and the extent to which pre-primary schools are accessible.

2.2 Concept of Education Planning

The strategy is educational planning, which focuses administration, the focus of the school board, educators, pupils, and community members on where the school system should go and how to get there. It assists in the identification of potential dangers in the immediate future. Without planning, the school district's operational and functional performance will be less than ideal, making it impossible to meet the district's overall objectives and goals. Educational planning is a systematic conceptual process in which administration, the school board, teachers, students, and members of the community all participate. As a consequence, long-term goals and objectives are established, as well as short-term execution of specific goals through the use of focused techniques, tactics, and strategies that will enable the school district to achieve long-term goals and objectives (Gbadamosi, 2005).

In general, planning is the process of creating priorities for future activities in an attempt to solve economic challenges in many sectors caused by restricted resources. It entails giving attention to a country's objectives, desires, and priorities. Educational planning is making decisions for future activities with the goal of reaching set goals by making the best use of finite resources. The scope of education planning includes curriculum planning, goal setting, and manpower within the education sector.

2.3 Curriculum Development as the Elements of Early Childhood Education

In Rwanda's scenario, in 2007, NCDC (2007) established ECE curriculum to guide families, guardians, caregivers, neighbors and teachers to manage child with special needs. The curriculum includes sections and children rights from preconception. As a result, the cooperation of Ministries of Education, Health, Social Development, and Culture was necessary. The same curriculum had no guidelines for educators (teachers). The ECE curriculum is now being reviewed, with plans to remedy gaps by adding core subjects such as reading, numeracy, exploring the word, art, crafts, and technology, as well as life skills (MINEDUC, 2015). The curriculum must be constantly modified because it must be relevant to societal needs, because society is not static; it is changing.

Construction of classrooms, standardized equipment and facilities in Rwandan nursery schools should include rooms and available learning and playing materials. In the few last years, pre-primary schooling has become widely available throughout the country, from parents and community. UNICEF provided ECD learning and play resources to 1,260 nursery schools in 2014 and trained 1,000 teachers on how to utilize the products in the classroom. (MINEDUC, 2015).

According to MINEDUC (2014), suitable games and learning materials for pre-primary schools include: Swings, ladders, rope, trees and nets, climbing and gym, rocking, roundabouts, bats and balls, toboggan/sliding games, balance and fitness, ropes, puzzles, small bicycles, small balls, big circles, hand puppets, cubes shapes, spring rockers, toys and so on. Preprimary education requires also enough and comfortable classrooms. Without those buildings and required facilities pre-primary schooling fails.

2.4 Concept of Early Childhood Education and Development

UNESCO and UNICEF (2012) outlined many phrases and meanings used in the Asia-Pacific area to refer to children under the age of eight and their education and care. Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE), Early Childhood Education, Care, and Development (ECECD), and Early Childhood Education and Development (ECED) are examples of these terms. They found that agreement on the scope and comprehensive character of ECCE is required. MINEDUC (2011) defines Early Childhood Development (ECD) as the process through which children grow and prosper physically, cognitively, emotionally, ethically, and socially from conception to the age of six. This comprises a variety of services offered to young children to help them grow holistically while also ensuring they are adequately cared for and successfully safeguarded.

According to the OECD (2014), early childhood education is connected with improved academic achievement later in life, aiding in the prevention of repeat and dropout in primary and secondary school. MINEDUC (2015), differentiated early childhood development from pre-primary or preschool. It designs the first one as broader which includes the time from infancy to 6 years of life, in the case the last one is the stage preparing children to primary education, which starts from 3 to 7 years of age. The International Labor Organization (2012) defines ECE as support for children aged six and under, considering the emphasis on education rather than care, the three- to six-year-old age group receives the most attention (and the majority of the accessible material). Briefly, pre-primary education implies the issues of formal education for children aged between three and six or seven to prepare them for primary education.

2.5 Early Childhood Education and Development Challenges

Regarding the expanding relevance of preschool education, there are several obstacles to its successful implementation. Among these include insufficient teaching and learning materials, socioeconomic concerns, a high teacher-to-child ratio with a low wage, and budgetary constraints.

Several ECDE centers need essential teaching and learning materials, as well as ECDE-appropriate spaces for learning. A lack of air-conditioned classrooms, suitable children's equipment, a kitchen, safe, clean water, a playground, toilets, and play items are among these (International Association for the Education of Young Children, 1991). This means that instructors lack enough teaching and learning materials to properly implement the ECDE Curriculum. This has a detrimental impact on the implementation of the ECDE Curriculum since building a lasting learning atmosphere helps poor students improve their performance in school (Offenheiser & Holcombe, 2003).

2.6 Accessibility to Early Childhood Education

According to UNESCO, cited in MINEDUC (2010), the international standard pupil/teacher ratio in pre-primary is 15:1. The pupil-to-teacher ratio in OECD countries ranges from more than 20 in Chile, France, Indonesia, Israel, Mexico, and Turkey to fewer than 10 in Indonesia, Iceland, New Zealand, Slovenia, and Sweden, according to the OECD (2014). Teachers' aides are commonly utilized at the preschool level in several nations. Pupil-to-contact-staff ratios were lower in 12 countries than pupil-to-teaching-staff ratios. As consequence, the pupil-to-contact-staff ratio is far lower than the pupil-to-teaching-staff ratio. In 2012, according to the Rwandan Population Housing Census, attendance has climbed to 29% of 1.28 million children aged 3 to 6 years. (MINECOFIN, 2014).

In 2013, there were 2,076 pre-primary schools across the country. Only 2 were Government owned, 523 were for Faith Based Organization, 1,410 for Parent Associations (Government-aided) and 141 for Individuals. Moreover, 60% of nursery schools were attached to 9YBE and can be classified as government-aided, because the government contributes largely to the EDC provision apart from salaries of educators. However, the pupil/teacher ratio is 35:1; instead, the international standard is 15:1 as recommended by UNICEF (MINEDUC, 2014).

2.7 Empirical Literature

In the study conducted by Ackerman (2006), in Lagos State, Nigeria assessed the influence of educational planning on early child education. Information was generated from primary as well as secondary sources. For this particular study, a total population of 2670 was used among which stratified sampling technique was employed to select 1000 upon which the research instruments were administered. According to the findings of the research educational planning has a significant impact on preschool education. The provision of educational materials and funds has promoted accessibility to early elementary school education in Lagos State.

Kadiri (2014) focused on the role of pre-services trainings program of instructors of young children's education in promoting availability to preschool education. The study emphasized the need to train more teachers to enhance the early childhood education program in Mwatate sub- country. The research comprised a population of 100 public preschool programs. A total of ten schools were picked at random from the sub-country. The study employed correlational research design for data analysis. According to the report, educational planners and policymakers should spend heavily in pre-service preparation for early childhood teachers since there is a dearth of well-trained educators in early childhood programs. Burchinal (2002) carried out a research study titled "educational planning and early childhood accessibility in selected Enungu state, Nigeria. The target population was two hundred forty (240) preprimary schools, of which twenty-four (24) were chosen as the sample using systematic sampling. A list of questions was utilized as the data gathering tool. For analysis of data, SPSS software was utilized. Three null hypotheses were presented and evaluated at a significance level of 1.00 using average weight responses test statistics. The null hypotheses were all accepted. The results shown that the accessibility of early childhood education depended upon the effective educational planning. It means that effective educational planning would promote early childhood education development.

The population of interest for the research consisted of 235 nursery schools, thirty (30) among which were chosen as the population to be studied. The major data gathering instrument was a questionnaire. Four (4) null study hypotheses were given in the research and evaluated with Chi-square(x2) test statistics at the 5% (0.05) level of significance. The results of the study demonstrated that in-service training had an important impact on early childhood education growth. Uyagu (2009) conducted a study named "The effects of infrastructure development on early childhood education promotion in nursery schools in Zaria LGA, Kadura state." The target population consisted of 1540 nursery school instructors from 24 nursery schools in Zaria Local Government Area.

2.8 Theoretical Framework

Theoretical framework consists in overview of theories used in what researcher intends to study. The utility of theory is to improve practice. No practice can be successful independently to an appropriate theory. It is for this reason this study needs to develop educational planning theories. As a result, the study will be directed by social demand theory and the manpower approach/ theory.

Education, according to this point of view, is a consumer good that should be made available to everyone as quickly as possible. This entails, on one side, calculating what the circumstance will be in regard to fees, educators' availability, plant and assets, and school leaver results at the completion of a defined planning time if present school provision is maintained more or less as is; and, on the other hand, calculating what the circumstances would look like and what would need to be done if different forms of community interest was met (Thompson, 1991). The estimations are used as a starting point for calculating planned system modifications, most notably the rating system. However, when resources are seriously limited, as they are in many African nations, and we are attempting to deliver the sort and volume knowledge that will benefit many people the most, such planning techniques, while beneficial, can't provide all of the advice we require in order to satisfy the requirements identified. This idea or method is relevant to this study because, despite Rwanda's government's limitations, early childhood education should be offered to all young children. It is required for all young children aged 3 to 6 years. As a result, it is a societal necessity.

3. RESEARCHER METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines different techniques utilized to conduct the research. The same part goes through the study design, target population, sample, sampling methods, research instruments, instrument validity, instrument reliability, data collection techniques, data processing methodology, and ethical issues.

3.1 Design of the Study

The research employed the Descriptive Survey Research Design, as well as both quantitative and qualitative research approaches. In this research, descriptive research method was utilized to answer issues on the influence of planning for education in early childhood education access. Besides from observed situation of all the villages of Gasabo District, concerning Early Childhood Education, the researcher was aware of the place where to locate more infrastructures. The researcher was also told of the number of instructors who would be trained to teach early childhood education and the areas where efforts would be made to raise awareness of pre-primary education so as to increase schools and children enrolled in pre-schools.

3.2 Target Population

The term population, in broad terms, refers to a collection of individuals who live in a specific geographical region; however, in study, this word is employed to describe all those who take part in an investigation; consequently, the audience is the team that is important to the investigator, the group to whom the researcher wants to extrapolate the research findings. According to Odera and Okenyi (2006), population refers to "all the numbers or elements; be they human beings, animals, trees, objects, events, etc, of a well-defined group." There are two types of populations in scientific research: target populations and reachable populations. The term "target population" relates to the real group chosen by the investigator to whom she or he would want to make conclusions. However, because it is uncommon, the investigator must depend on the present community. The sample size from which the researcher may draw equitable conclusions (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2003). The decrease in quantity because of the reason that he intended audience is generally very vast, requiring a lot of time, effort, and money. In this study therefore, the target population includes 15 Sector Education Officers in Gasabo District, 155 head teachers, 471 teachers and 465 parents' committee members.

3.3 Size of the Sample

Because it was impossible to study the impact of education planning to accessibility to early childhood education on the whole District of Gasabo, a small number of respondents was selected.

3.4 Techniques of Sampling

The practice of selecting a specified number of persons from a given group to represent that population is known as sampling. A statement about the sample must additionally be true for the population (Orodho, 2012). However, it is widely accepted that the greater the sample size, the lower the sampling error (Gay, 19992).

The researcher used two techniques of sampling: stratified random sampling and purposive sampling. The stratified approach entails separating the population into important strata, which were determined by the number of nursery schools in the Gasabo District. In turn, stratified random sampling was chosen for its advantages of paying attention on important particular populations and permitting the employment of multiple sample procedures for distinct subpopulations, as a result improving estimate accuracy. The number of sector education officers and school principals was chosen using a purposive sampling approach.

3.5 Data Collection Methods

This study's data was qualitative and quantitative, and it was derived from primary as well as secondary sources. Primary resources were gathered from field study, whereas secondary sources were obtained through literature. During the field inquiry, information was gathered using questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions.

3.6 Data Collection Instrument Administration

As it was research in Gasabo District, the researcher had to write to Mayor, requesting for conducting research in this administrative entity.

Interview

To gather data by administrating interview, the researcher must contact concerned persons, justify the motive of enquiry and ask for appointment which must be scheduled according to the availability of respondents. In this study interview was conducted with sector education officers.

Questionnaire

Questionnaires were administered by researcher in different nursery schools selected. They were handed to teachers and Head Teachers. The instruments were retaken in the same way, after two days in order to avoid higher missing returns.

Focus Group Discussions

Interview guide for the focus group was conducted in accordance with respondents' availability which was agreed upon on the phone, the researcher hired a room for participants to feel free from any kind of disturbances which could occur. It lasted about one hour and a half. The FGD targeted a group of parents' representatives from selected schools. The place and venue were agreed upon in advance. During the FGD members' interview process, the researcher took notes using a pen and sheets

of paper to record all of the information from the respondents. All in all, according to Burton and Steane (2004) the quantitative analysis relies on statistics while qualitative analysis supplements via furnishing deep understanding of the topic under investigation.

3.7 Data Analysis Procedure

Descriptive design is concerned with portraying circumstances as they are and hence strives to provide as truthful and accurate a description as possible. The design of a correlation research, on the other hand, helps in identifying whether and how far a relationship exists between two or more factors. The greatest percentage and mean were used in reporting the research findings. Pearson Correlation was utilized to examine the connection between factors in objective three of the study.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter highlights the study's findings based on data from the field. The study's goal was to look at the link between education planning and access to early childhood education in Rwanda's Gasabo District. The research questions influenced the presentations and an examination of the significant link between the variables chosen for the study. The information provided by the data results of analysis provided a basis for the study's discussion, conclusion, and interpretation of its results and recommendations.

4.1 Respondents' Category

The researcher initially attempted to categorize respondents, from whom information were gathered from. The researcher included four major categories namely sector education officers, head teachers, teachers and parents. The types of respondents that took part in this survey. It shows that 47 teachers 47(42.7 %), 15 Head teachers (13.6 %) and 46 parents (41.8 %) were involved in the study. While (2 1.8 %) sector education officers participated also in the study. Whitebread (2010) Suggested that data must be corrected from different categories of respondents so as to be considered true.

4.2 Presentation of results

The goal of this research was to look at the link between Education Planning and pre-primary Education Accessibility. The candidate used Spearman correlation to test the nature of link between variables. The researcher also used some statistical techniques like Mean and Standard Deviation for descriptive statistics.

4.3 Education Planning

Educational planning is the process of developing strategies, policies, procedures, programs, and standards beforehand to attain educational objectives. The current research looks into the availability of elements of education planning in Gasabo District namely training of staff, curriculum development and construction, equipment and facilities. Table 4.6, 4.7 and 4.8 show the perception of respondents on availability of elements of education planning in Gasabo District.

Table 1: Respondents' perspectives on staff training

Training of staff	Mean	Std. Deviation
Teachers who teach in nursery schools have received pre-service training in pre-primary education (have a certificate in pre-school education)	2.27	1.241
Nursery school teachers receive continuous in-service trainings so as to be up to date	2.47	1.186
The head teacher of nursery schools in Gasabo District are qualified in early childhood education	2.43	1.104
Teachers in nursery schools often receive workshop and seminars about the use of teaching and learning materials.	2.52	1.150
Average	2.4225	1.17025

Table 1 demonstrates the opinion of participants on training of staff as an element of education Planning. According to table 4.6, a large number of those who responded disagreed with the item that instructors who teach in nursery schools have received preliminary training in pre-primary education (have a certificate in the domain of preschool education), as

demonstrated by the mean of 2.27, that is considered a low mean. It means that the majority of instructors in Gasabo District's nursery schools are not educated in pre-school education, which can lead to poor teaching owing to a lack of skills and understanding in education for young children. Therefore, there is a need for training of nursery school instructors in early childhood education. When the researcher examined whether the Nursery school educators receive continuous in-service trainings so as to be up to date, the results in Table 4.6 indicated a mean of 2.47 that is understood as having a low mean. This means that the majority of respondents also disagreed about this second item. The investigation also discovered that many of responses contradicted the assertion that the head teachers of nursery schools in Gasabo District are competent in early childhood education, as evidenced by a mean of 2.03. This suggests that head of the schools in pre-primary education profession require training so as to carry out their duties successfully and efficiently.

In examining whether teachers in nursery schools often receive workshop and seminars about the use of instructional and learning materials, findings in the diagram 4.6 indicated that a large number of those asked disagreed regarding the issue. This implies that the available nursery schools do not organize workshop and seminars about the use of learning and teaching materials so as to upgrade the knowledge and skills in education of young children. During interview with sector education officers, majority of them claimed that most of teachers in preschool education are not trained in pre-primary education. As a result, this has an impact on the learning and teaching processes in pre-primary schools.

Table 2: Perception of respondents on curriculum development

Curriculum development	Mean	Std. Deviation
There is a well-designed national curriculum for nursery schools	2.59	1.241
All nursery schools in Gasabo District follow a National curriculum	2.36	1.197
Some nursery schools use curriculum from other countries	3.61	1.242
The curriculum used in nursery school is stimulating and developmentally appropriate	2.29	1.176
Average	2.7125	1.214

The survey intended to examine the extent to which respondents perceive the following items. The majority of responders, according to the statistics in Table 2, disagreed on the item that there is a well-designed national curriculum for nursery schools, as shown by a mean of 2.59, which is expressed as low mean. As seen by a mean of 2.36, a big number of respondents also did not agree with the second declaration, that all nursery schools in Gasabo District follow a National curriculum. In addition, during the interview conducted with sector education officers, they said that private nursery schools use curriculum from other countries like Congo, Uganda and Burundi in addition to the national curriculum and this interferes with the proper implementation of national curriculum. This implies that all children in nursery schools are not being taught the same content which is not good for preparing young children for standardized primary education. In analyzing whether some nursery schools use curriculum from other countries, the results in the mean in Table 2 is 3.61, which is taken as a high mean. This means that the majority of participants confirmed that some nursery schools that some nursery schools especially private schools use curriculum from other countries in addition to national program.

Table 3: Perception of respondents on construction, equipment and facilities

Construction, equipment and facilities	Mean	Std. Deviation
Our school has enough classrooms for learners	2.12	1.225
Our school has enough latrines specialized to young children	2.22	1.087
Your school has enough chairs and desks to young children	2.38	1.234
Our school has enough played materials for learners such as swings, ladders, ropes, bats and balls	2.14	1.208
The school has enough text books for learning	2.10	1.306
Average	2.192	1.212

Table 3 illustrates the opinion of respondents on construction, equipment and facilities as an element of education planning. The majority of participants disagreed with the first question, "Our school has enough classrooms for learners," as evidenced by a mean of 2.12 that is viewed as a low mean. This implies that the nursery schools in Gasabo District are facing the problem of insufficient classrooms. In examining whether nursery school has enough latrines specialized to young children, the findings in this table demonstrated a mean of 2.22, which is considered a low mean.

This shows that most of respondents have divergent views on this issue. This implies that young children in nursery schools share latrines with elders of primary schools due to the fact that most nursery schools are attached to primary schools and as a result of insufficient funds, schools could not manage to have different latrines for different levels of studies. Results in Table 4.8, further indicate that nursery schools in Gasabo District do not have enough chairs and desks for young children as shown by the mean of 2.38 and available ones are not appropriate to young children as observed by the researcher. Young children use the same kind of chairs and desks like those of their elders of primary level. Yet they are too young to sit on them. Therefore, there is a need to offer proper seats and desks for young children in order for them to study more effectively. The researcher went further to examine whether nursery schools have enough played materials for learners such as swings, ladders, ropes, bats and balls. The results indicated a mean of 2.14 which is expressed as low mean. This signifies that the majority of respondents disapprove with this issue. This implies that nursery schools are facing the problem of shortage of playing materials for learners.

Finally, the researcher determined the amount to which the respondents value the final item. Based on the information given, many of respondents disagreed with the statement that the school has enough text books for learning, as seen by the mean of 2.10; this is translated as a low mean. According to the findings of interviews with sector education officials, there is a problem with insufficient infrastructure, equipment, and facilities in our schools, which impedes the implementation of early childhood programs.

4.4 Relationship between planning and accessibility to Early Childhood Education

This section discusses the connection between educational planning and access to early childhood education. The Spearman correlation coefficient approach was employed by the investigator must ascertain the nature of connection.

Table 4: Relationship between education planning and accessibility to ECE

Education planning		Accessibility to early ECE
Training of staff	Pearson Correlation	.741**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
Curriculum Development	Pearson Correlation	.638**
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000
Equipment	Pearson Correlation	.879**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

** .Correlation is significant at 0.01 (2-tailed) level.

Table 4 demonstrates the association across education planning and Early Childhood Education accessibility. As displayed in table 4, there is a positive connection across staff training and access to early childhood education with a correlation coefficient of 0.741. Given that the Sig. (2-tailed) p-value is less than 0.01 this is significant in statistical terms. Second, the correlation coefficient of 0.638 indicates a positive association between curriculum development and access to early childhood education, which is statistically significant given that Sig. (2-tailed) p-value is 0.000, which is less than 0.01. Furthermore, the results demonstrate a positive relationship between construction, equipment and facilities and accessibility to early childhood education due to the correlation coefficient of 0.89 and that is statistically important since the Sig.(2-tailed) p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.01. According to the results in table 4 the researcher concluded that education planning greatly influences accessibility to early childhood education.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The chapter five evaluates the study's outcomes, which were reported in fourth chapter. It also includes the study's results and suggestions, which could improve the accessibility to early childhood education. Moreover, recommendations for more research were provided.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The primary goal of this research was to discover the association between education planning and access to early childhood education in the Gasabo District. A questionnaire was employed as the primary data collection instrument to collect information from 110 respondents. The researcher employed statistical approaches for example, mean and standard deviation to respond to the first and second objectives. The investigator utilised the Spearman correlation coefficient to evaluate the nature of the link across variables. The study's findings demonstrated a favourable association between the elements of education planning employed in this research and access to Early Childhood Education.

5.2 Conclusions

According to results of the research, the elements of education planning in Gasabo District such as training of staff, curriculum development and construction, equipment and facilities were not sufficient. This implies that there is a shortage of certified early childhood educators, as well as a lack of standardized nursery curricula and teaching and learning materials for young children. In addition, the researcher found that there is limited access to early childhood education in Gasabo District as explained by high students' teacher ratio, unequal distribution of nursery schools in Gasabo district and poor physical setting aspect of available schools. This means that some young children do not attend nursery school, due to a lack of construction and equipment, as well as teaching and learning tools for young children. Finally, the findings of the study demonstrated a substantial association between education planning and access to early childhood education.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the study's results and conclusions, the following suggestions were created: The research recommends that in service training and pre-service trainings in the domain of Early Childhood Education should be provided to more teaching staff. This could be done by training more students in Preschool education in higher learning institutions in Rwanda and by establishing in service training centers for early childhood education educators. The research also suggests that the curriculum used in nursery schools be standardized so that the content may be changed and customized to the level of young learners. Finally, the study suggests that education planners and policymakers prioritize early childhood education throughout budget planning and formulation. This could help in provision of sufficient equipment, buildings and teaching and learning resources.

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